

THE INFLUENCE OF ALLOY ELEMENTS ON THE PROPERTIES OF CARBON FIBER AND C/Cu COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

The influence of alloy elements (Cu, Ni, Cr) on the properties and structure of carbon fiber has been studied by means of the continuous electrodeposition of metals on fiber surface and vacuum heat treatment. It is shown that the fiber strength is decreased because of the diffusion between nickel and carbon and the formation of chromic carbide on fiber surface; copper can act as a barrier to restrain the diffusion of nickel to fiber surface, but it cannot act as a diffusion barrier of chromium, whereas nickel has obvious effect to retard the diffusion of chromium to fiber surface. The results suggest that the diffusion process can be influenced noticeably if solid solution is formed between the coated metals. The longitudinal strength of c/cu composite is raised to 650 Mpa by continuous electrodeposition of copper-nickel-copper on fiber surface and hot pressing, so it is feasible to increase the strength of c/cu composite by controlling the chemical reaction of interface.

INTRODUCTION

The carbon fiber reinforced copper (C/Cu) composite has received the great attention to be used as the electron material, brush material, wear resistance and heat resistance material because of its predominant properties [1][2], such as high strength, high modulus, high wear resistance, excellent conductivities of electricity and heat, and the stabilities of size and properties at elevated temperature.

However, the fabrication of C/Cu composite is difficult and complex, because of the high melting point of copper and poor wetability between copper and carbon fibers [3]. It was reported that electrodeposition method is a cheap and efficacious way to manufacture C/Cu composite [4]. Because the compatibility of copper and carbon fiber is excellent, and no chemical reaction occurs between copper and carbon fiber even at high temperature, the combination of copper matrix with carbon fibers is limited to physical state in C/Cu composite; so how to increase the chemical interface combination and obtain the best interfacial combination is the key to improve the property of C/Cu composite.

In the experiment, continuous electrodeposition was performed to deposit several different metals on fiber surface, and the parameters of electrodeposition and heat treatment were changed to obtain the different degree of chemical reaction at interface. The properties and structure of carbon fibers coated with Ni, Cu-Ni, Ni-Cu, Cu-Cr and Ni-Cu are studied after heat treated at different temperatures; and the influence of chemical combination at interface on the properties of C/Cu composite is discussed to seek the best interfacial combination and improve the properties of C/Cu composite.

EXPERIMENT

The properties of carbon fiber, made in China, used in the experiment were as follows: tensile strength 1960Mpa, elastic modulus 196 GPa, density 1.65 g/cm³, diameter 6-8 μm and carbon content > 94%.

The matrix material was electrolytic copper, the copper content was 99.9% and its tensile strength was 232 Mpa. The reagents used in electrodeposition were chemically pure.

In the experiment, the electrodeposition were used to deposit different desired metals on carbon fiber surface and the parameters of each step can be adjusted respectively. The fiber should be pre-treated before electrodeposition, it includes mainly oil clearing, coarsing, rinsing and drying.

The solution for plating copper was alkaline complex solution, it has a good wettability to carbon fiber, and low deposition rate, copper can be coated on each fiber surface uniformly in the solution. The solution for plating nickel was Ni²⁺ ion complex solution and is chromate solution for plating chromium. The carbon fibers coated with desired metals were electrodeposited in acid solution of plating copper to obtain C/Cu composite containing desired volume fraction of fibers.

The carbon fibers after electrodeposited were heat treated in various temperatures at vacuum more than 2×10^{-4} torr. The temperatures of heat treatment were 500°C, 600°C, 700°C, 800°C, 900°C and 1000°C, the soaking times were 15 min. and 30 min. The C/Cu composite obtained by electrodeposition were hot pressed at vacuum more than 10^{-3} torr.

The carbon fibers after heat treated were tested and analyzed with ZLL-30 tension tester and PSEM 500x Energy Diffraction Spectrometer to determine the change of property and chemical composition, and the structures were observed with optical microscope and SEM.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The diameter of carbon fibers coated with metals will be changed with the change of electrodeposition parameters. To compare the effect of different procedure on the strength of fibers, a relative change of fiber strength, σ_{HT}/σ_0 , is used in strength-temperature curves, where σ_0 and σ_{HT} are the strength of fibers coated with metals before and after heat treated respectively.

1. The influence of nickel on carbon fiber properties and structure
The relationships between the strengths of carbon fiber coated with nickel and treating temperature are shown in Fig.1. It can be seen that the fiber strength does not change obviously when heat treated below 600°C, but a severe decrease of strength occurs above 600°C, and the fiber strength after heat treated at 800°C is only 15% of that of untreated. It was proved [5] that the mutual diffusion will occur between nickel and carbon fiber at elevated temperature, and nickel possesses the catalytic effect on graphitizing of carbon fiber. It can be seen that, as shown in Fig.2, the interfacial diffusion has occurred noticeably, and the interface between nickel and carbon fiber becomes unclear and migrates into the carbon fiber forming an unsmooth interface, it results in the reduce of cross-section of carbon fiber and graphitization of carbon fiber, and the severe decrease of fiber strength.

2. The influence of coated copper and nickel on the properties of carbon fiber

Since the direct diffusion of nickel to carbon fiber results in the

Fig.1. Variation of strength of Ni coated fiber with temperature. (a) Coating 4 min., (b) Coating 6 min

Fig.2. Micrograph of the carbon fiber coated with Ni(SEM), (a) Untreated, (b) Heat treated at 900°C, 30 min.

severe decrease of fiber strength, so a diffusion barrier is designed between nickel and carbon fiber to restrain the diffusion of nickel and to control the interfacial reaction. Copper might act as a diffusion barrier, because no reaction occurs between copper and carbon and the diffusion coefficient of carbon in copper is almost zero [6], hence, the carbon fibers are coated with copper and nickel and then heat treated to study the influence of copper on the diffusion of nickel and the property of carbon fiber.

The variations of fiber strength coated with Cu-Ni with the temperature are shown in Fig.3. It can be seen that the strength of most fibers begins to decrease in 700°C to 800°C, and drops down to 45% that of untreated fibers at 800°C. Since no reaction occurs between copper and carbon, the decrease of fiber strength is also due to the diffusion of nickel to fiber surface and resulting in the graphitization of carbon fiber.

Comparing the strengths of fibers coated with Cu-Ni and Ni (Fig.1. and 3.) shows that the strength of fibers coated with Cu-Ni is much better than that coated with Ni after heat treated at 800°C. It is indicated that the damage of carbon fiber is decreased.

The thickness of copper layer also has influence on the diffusion of nickel, see Fig. 3(d). It indicated that fiber can be protected from

Fig.3 Variation of strength of Cu-Ni coated fiber with temperature, coating Ni 6min, coating Cu (a) 4 min, (b) 6 min, (c) 8 min, (d) 15 min.

chemical damage of nickel if the copper layer is thick enough and can remain its strength to higher temperature. But the thickness of copper will influence the volume fraction of fiber in composite and then influence the properties of composite.

The nickel distribution after heat treated is shown in Fig.4. The nickel content at the interface is decreased, and hence the chemical damage of nickel to fiber is restrained.

Consequently, copper can act as the barrier to restrain the diffusion of nickel to fiber, the diffusion process and the interfacial reaction degree can be controlled by adjusting the parameters of heat treatment to obtain the best interfacial state.

Fig.4 Distribution of Ni in coated layer after heat treated.

3. The influence of coated copper and nickel on the properties of C/Cu composite

To investigate the influence of interfacial reaction on the properties of C/Cu composite, the composite obtained by continuous electrodeposition of Cu-Ni-Cu on fiber are hot pressed at 700°C and 800°C. In this temperature range, according to the analysis above, a certain degree of interfacial reaction can be obtained and carbon fibers have enough

strength. The hot press parameters and the tensile strength of composite are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. The tensile strength of Cu - Ni - Cu composite after hot pressed

	hot press temperature (°C)	soaking time (min)	pressure (Mpa)	volume fraction of fiber (%)	tensile strength (Mpa)
1	700	40	10	26	573
2	800	40	10	26	648
3(a)	700	40	10	26	586

(a) Here '3' is the highest tensile strength of C/Cu composite coated with copper.

It can be seen that the strength of composite coated with Cu-Ni-Cu is increased noticeably to 650Mpa after hot pressed at 800°C, which is higher than the best value 586Mpa of C/Cu composite. The results indicate that a better interfacial combination is obtained after hot pressed at 800°C in C/Cu-Ni-Cu composite. Although the decrease of fiber strength is more severe after heat treated at 800°C than at 700°C, when the composites coated with Cu-Ni-Cu are hot pressed, nickel diffuses into both side copper layers and form solid solution with copper, it makes the amount of nickel diffused to fiber surface less, and so that the same degree of chemical reaction will be obtained at higher temperature. On the other hand, the formation of solid solution of nickel and copper may strengthen the matrix. Consequently, it is feasible to increase the strength of C/Cu composite by controlling the chemical reaction of interface.

4. The influence of chromium on the property and structure of carbon fiber

Chromium is carbide forming element. It is difficult to deposit chromium directly on the fiber surface, and the reaction between carbon fiber and chromium is severe and uneasy to control. So a layer of copper and nickel is pre-deposited before the deposition of chromium to increase the electric conductivity of carbon fiber and act as a diffusion barrier.

(1) properties of Cu-Cr coated fiber

The variation of strength of fiber coated with Cu-Cr is shown in Fig.5. The strength of fiber drops rapidly even heat treated at lower temperature (600°C), and is almost zero above 800°C. The distribution of chromium is shown in Fig.6. The chromium content at interface is higher after heat treated at various temperatures. These indicated that copper has little effect on diffusion of chromium and it cannot protect carbon fiber from the damage of chromium.

(a)

(b)

Fig.5 Variation of strength of Cu-Cr coated fiber with temperature, coating Cu 6 min, coating Cr (a) 1 min, (b) 3 min.

Fig.6 Distribution of Cr in coated layer after heat treated.

Fig.7 Micrograph of fiber coated with Cu-Cr, heat treated at 900°C, 30 min.

The observation of structure (as shown in Fig.7) indicates that chromic carbides are formed on surface of fiber after heat treatment. The carbides will act as the cracks and notches on fiber surface, and result in the stress concentration and the reduce of efficient cross-section of fibers. So that the strength of carbon fiber decrease severely.

(2) Properties of Ni-Cr coated fiber

The variation of strength of fibers coated with Ni-Cr is shown in Fig.8. The strength of fiber coated with Ni-Cr is much better than that of fiber

Fig.8 Variation of strength of Ni-Cr coated fiber with temperature, coating Ni:6 min, and Cr: 10 min

Fig.9 Distribution of Cr in coated layer after heat treated at 900°C, 30 min

coated with Cu-Cr after heat treated at various temperatures, and is 45% of that untreated fibers at 800°C. In our opinion, it is the results of interaction between different metal atoms and its influence on diffusion. According to the constitutional diagrams of Cu-Cr and Ni-Cr, below 900°C, neither compound nor solid solution are formed between copper and chromium, whereas the solubility of chromium in nickel is about 40% and the solubility of nickel in chromium is 7% at 900°C, they form solid solution in a wide range. After the solid solution formed between metals, the migration of atoms is restrained by each other, and the diffusion velocity of both metal atoms is delayed. Hence, nickel can act as the barrier of chromium diffusion and its diffusion is restricted by chromium also, to the contrary, copper has little effect on diffusion of chromium. It can be proved by distribution of chromium, as shown in Fig.9, the chromium content at interface is much lower in fiber coated with Ni-Cr

than in fiber coated with Cu-Cr. Hence nickel has a obvious effect on reducing the damage of chromium to fiber.

Based on the above analysis, it is considered that the solid solutions are formed between Cu and Ni, as well as Ni and Cr, so the diffusion is influenced noticeably; no solid solution is formed between Cu and Cr, so there is little effect on diffusions between them. It can be assumed that if solid solutions are formed between metals, they can act as barrier to restrain diffusion, if not, the influence on diffusion is not obvious.

CONCLUSION

1. The strength of carbon fiber coated with nickel decreases severely after vacuum heat treated at 700°C, because of the diffusion of nickel to fiber. Copper can act as the barrier of nickel diffusion and the effect will be more obvious if the thickness of copper is suitable.
2. The strength of composite coated with Cu-Ni-Cu is up to 650Mpa after hot pressed at 800°C, and it is better than that of C/Cu composite. It is feasible to improve the properties of C/Cu composite by controlling chemical reaction at interface.
3. The formation of chromic carbide on the surface of carbon fiber results in the severe decrease of fiber strength even heat treated at low temperature. Copper cannot act as the barrier to restrain the diffusion of chromium to carbon fiber.
4. The strength of carbon fibers coated with Ni-Cr is much better than that of fibers coated with Cu-Cr after heat treatment. Nickel has notable effect on chromium diffusion, and can act as a barrier of chromium diffusion.
5. Through the study of coating layer Cu-Ni, Cu-Cr and Ni-Cr, it can be concluded that if solid solution is formed between metals, they can act as barrier to restrain diffusion; if no solid solution are formed, they have little influence on diffusion. This is significant to control the chemical reaction at interface.

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